

Bernoulli collocation method for solving a model of HIV infection of CD4⁺T cells

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ABSTRACT

This manuscript is devoted to introduce a numerical method for solving a model of the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection of CD4⁺T cells. This model is a system of nonlinear differential equations. A collocation method based on Bernoulli polynomials is applied to solve this model, numerically. Employing the proposed method, the model is reduced to a system of nonlinear algebraic equations. The efficiency and effectiveness of the present method are studied by comparing numerical results of our method and some existing method.

KEYWORDS: Bernoulli polynomials, HIV infection, Collocation method, Nonlinear differential equations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Mathematical models are valuable for understanding natural problems. Scientists solve important models by solving these problems. A major problem for human health in recent decades is Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS). The most well-known models of immune deficiency virus (HIV) models have been developed by Perlson et al. [1] which is described by the system of ordinary nonlinear differential equations. Many other models are currently proposed that have inspired this model. CD4⁺T cells, also known as leukocytes or helper T cells, play a key role in protecting the body against diseases. Typically, the number of T helper cells in a healthy person is about 800-1200 mm^3 , and HIV viruses use these cells to spread and weaken the immune system. This model consists of three components. Concentrations of CD4⁺T-cells, CD4⁺T-cells infected with HIV and free HIV particles in the blood are determined by $T(t)$, $I(t)$ and $V(t)$, respectively.

This model is formulated as a system of three nonlinear DDEs as follows

$$\begin{cases} T'(t) = \alpha - \beta T(t) + \gamma T(t) \left(1 - \frac{T(t) + I(t)}{T_{max}}\right) - \delta V(t)T(t), \\ I'(t) = \delta V(t)T(t) - \varepsilon I(t), \\ V'(t) = \theta \varepsilon I(t) - \vartheta V(t), \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

with initial conditions

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$$T(0) = \mu_0, \quad I(0) = \mu_1, \quad V(0) = \mu_2, \quad 0 \leq t \leq l < \infty. \quad (2)$$

Moreover, we consider $\mu_0 = \mu_2 = 0.1, \mu_1 = 0$ and the parameters in this model are described in Table 1.

Table 1. Description and intended value of different parameters in HIV CD4⁺T cells model [2].

Parameters	Intended value	Description
α	0.1	Rate of CD4 ⁺ T cells produced in body
β	0.02	Natural turnover rates of uninfected T cells
γ	3	Growth rate of CD4 ⁺ T cell
δ	0.0027	Infection rate
ε	0.3	Natural turnover rate of infected T cells
ϑ	2.4	Natural turnover rate of virus particles
T_{max}	1500	The maximum CD4 ⁺ T cell concentration in the body
θ	10	Virus particles produced by infected CD4 ⁺ T cells
$\delta V(t)I(t)$	–	The incidence of HIV infection of healthy CD4 ⁺ T cells
$1 - \frac{T(t) + I(t)}{T_{max}}$	–	The logistic growth of the healthy CD4 ⁺ T cells

Also, several numerical methods have been used to solve the mathematical modelling of HIV, such as Homotopy analysis method [3], Bessel collocation method [4], Legendre wavelet method [5], and so on.

2 PRELIMINARIES

2.1 Bernoulli polynomials

Bernoulli polynomials of order m is defined on $[0, 1]$ as

$$\beta_m(t) = \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} \alpha_{m-i} t^i, \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha_i, i = 0, 1, \dots, m$, are Bernoulli numbers and defined as:

$$\frac{t}{e^t - 1} = \sum_{i=0}^m \alpha_i \frac{t^i}{i!}.$$

The first few Bernoulli numbers are

$$\alpha_0 = 1, \quad \alpha_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, \quad \alpha_2 = \frac{1}{6}, \quad \alpha_4 = -\frac{1}{30}, \dots,$$

with $\alpha_{2i+1}, i = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$.

The first few Bernoulli polynomials are

$$\beta_0(t) = 1, \quad \beta_1(t) = t - \frac{1}{2}, \quad \beta_2(t) = t^2 - t + \frac{1}{6}, \dots$$

The following formula is satisfied for these polynomials [6]

$$\int_0^1 \beta_n(t)\beta_m(t) dt = (-1)^{n-1} \frac{m! n!}{(m+n)!} \alpha_{n+m} \quad n, m \geq 1.$$

According to [7], Bernoulli polynomials form a complete basis over the interval [0, 1].

2.2 Function approximation

It is obvious that

$$Y = \text{span}\{\beta_0(t), \beta_1(t), \dots, \beta_m(t)\}$$

is a finite dimensional and closed subspace of the Hilbert space $H = L^2 [0; 1]$, also Y is a complete subspace and there is a unique best approximation out of Y such as $f_0 \in Y$ for each $f \in H$, that is

$$\forall y \in Y, \quad \|f(t) - f_0(t)\| \leq \|f(t) - y(t)\|.$$

Since $f_0 \in Y$ there exists unique coefficients c_0, c_1, \dots, c_m such that

$$f(t) \approx f_0(t) = \sum_{j=0}^m c_j \beta_j(t) = C^T \Psi(t).$$

Where T indicates transposition, C and $\Psi(t)$ are vectors given by:

$$C = [c_0, c_1, \dots, c_m]^T, \quad \Psi(t) = [\beta_0(t), \beta_1(t), \dots, \beta_m(t)]^T. \quad (4)$$

And C is defined as

$$C = D^{-1} \langle f, \Psi \rangle, \quad (5)$$

where \langle, \rangle denotes inner product and the entries of the matrix $D = (d_{i+1, j+1})$, $i, j = 0, \dots, m$ are given as follows:

$$d_{i+1, j+1} = \int_0^1 \beta_i(t)\beta_j(t) dt.$$

3 INTEGRATION OPERATIONAL MATRIX

Using Eq. (3), we can see that Bernoulli polynomials can be written as linear combinations of Taylor polynomials. Then, considering Eq. (4), we have

$$\Psi(t) = \Theta \phi(t), \quad \phi(t) = [1, t, \dots, t^m]^T, \quad (6)$$

where Θ is the transformation matrix of Bernoulli polynomials to the Taylor polynomials.

Now, we derive

$$\int_0^t \Psi(s) ds \approx P \Psi(t), \quad (7)$$

In which P is integration operational matrix of Bernoulli polynomials. For this approach, using Eq. (6), we obtain

$$\int_0^t \Psi(s) ds = \int_0^t \Theta \phi(s) ds = \Theta \int_0^t \phi(s) ds \approx \Theta \tilde{P} \phi(t), \quad (8)$$

where \tilde{P} is integration operation matrix of Taylor polynomials. Then, using Eqs. (6) and (8), we get

$$\int_0^t \Psi(s) ds \approx \Theta \tilde{P} \phi(t) = \Theta \tilde{P} \Theta^{-1} \Psi(t) = P \Psi(t),$$

where $P = \Theta \tilde{P} \Theta^{-1}$ is integration operational matrix of Bernoulli polynomials.

4 NUMERICAL METHOD

Considering model of HIV in Eq. (1), we can expanded the following functions using Bernoulli polynomials as

$$T'(t) = A^T \Psi(t), \quad I'(t) = B^T \Psi(t), \quad V'(t) = C^T \Psi(t). \quad (9)$$

Then, considering initial conditions, we have

$$T(t) = A^T P \Psi(t) + 0.1, \quad I(t) = B^T P \Psi(t), \quad V(t) = C^T P \Psi(t) + 0.1, \quad (10)$$

By substituting Eqs. (9)- (10) in Eq.(1), we achieve

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} A^T \Psi(t) - 0.1 + 0.03(A^T P \Psi(t) + 0.1) - 3(A^T P \Psi(t) + 0.1) \left(1 - \frac{(A^T P \Psi(t) + 0.1) + (B^T P \Psi(t))}{1500} \right) \\ \quad + 0.0027 (C^T P \Psi(t) + 0.1)(A^T P \Psi(t) + 0.1) = 0, \\ B^T \Psi(t) - 0.0027 (C^T P \Psi(t) + 0.1)(A^T P \Psi(t) + 0.1) + 0.3 (B^T P \Psi(t)) = 0, \\ C^T \Psi(t) - 3 (B^T P \Psi(t)) + 2.4 (C^T P \Psi(t) + 0.1) = 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (11)$$

Now, by using collocation method in nodes of $t_i = \frac{i}{m}, i = 0, 1, \dots, m$, and by applying "Find Root Package" in "Mathematica software", we can achieve the unknown vectors A, B and C .

5 NUMERICAL RESULTS

We apply the present method with $m = 10$ for solving this problem. Figure 1 shows the approximate solutions of $T(t), I(t)$ and $V(t)$. Also, Tables 1-3 demonstrate the comparison of numerical results for approximate solutions of $T(t), I(t)$ and $V(t)$ between Bessel collocation method [4], variational iteration method [8], Homotopy decomposition method [3] and the present method in different values of t and m . In these tables, the accuracy and convergence of the present method is well illustrated. For more investigation, we present graphs of residual norm for this system in $m = 20$ in Figure 2.

$$\begin{cases} R_1(t) = A^T \Psi(t) - 0.1 + 0.03(A^T P\Psi(t) + 0.1) - 3(A^T P\Psi(t) + 0.1) \left(1 - \frac{(A^T P\Psi(t) + 0.1) + (B^T P\Psi(t))}{1500}\right) \\ \quad + 0.0027 (C^T P\Psi(t) + 0.1)(A^T P\Psi(t) + 0.1), \\ R_2(t) = \Psi(t) - 0.0027 (C^T P\Psi(t) + 0.1)(A^T P\Psi(t) + 0.1) + 0.3 (B^T P\Psi(t)), \\ R_3(t) = C^T \Psi(t) - 3 (B^T P\Psi(t)) + 2.4 (C^T P\Psi(t) + 0.1), \end{cases}$$

Figure 1. The approximate solutions of (a) $T(t)$, (b) $I(t)$, (c) $V(t)$.

Table 2. Comparison of numerical results for $T(t)$ in different values of t .

Method	$t = 0.2$	$t = 0.6$	$t = 1$
Bessel collocation method	0.2038616561	0.6954623767	2.3832277428
Variational iteration method	0.2088073214	0.7624530350	2.5067466690
Homotopy decomposition method	0.2088072731	0.7611467713	2.3291697610
Present method ($m = 10$)	0.208808089108	0.76442388704	2.5915949176
Present method ($m = 15$)	0.208808084326	0.76442389850	2.5915948517
Present method ($m = 20$)	0.208808084326	0.76442389850	2.5915948517

Table 3. Numerical results for $I(t)$ in different values of t .

Method	$t = 0.2$	$t = 0.6$	$t = 1$
Bessel collocation method	$6.24787210e^{-6}$	$2.03526718e^{-5}$	$3.6908424 e^{-5}$
Variational iteration method	$6.03263437e^{-6}$	$2.10141719e^{-5}$	$2.4315623 e^{-5}$
Homotopy decomposition method	$6.03270728e^{-6}$	$2.12683688e^{-5}$	$3.9873654e^{-5}$
Present method ($m = 10$)	$6.0327015 e^{-6}$	$2.1223784 e^{-5}$	$4.003782 e^{-5}$
Present method ($m = 15$)	$6.0327022 e^{-6}$	$2.1223785 e^{-5}$	$4.003781 e^{-5}$
Present method ($m = 20$)	$6.0327022 e^{-6}$	$2.1223785 e^{-5}$	$4.003781 e^{-5}$

Table 4. Numerical results for $V(t)$ in different values of t .

Method	$t = 0.2$	$t = 0.6$	$t = 1$
Bessel collocation method	0.061879919	0.023704319	0.02370432
Variational iteration method	0.061879953	0.023920293	0.01608419
Homotopy decomposition method	0.061879960	0.024391743	0.00330508
Present method ($m = 10$)	0.061879841	0.023704550	0.00910076
Present method ($m = 15$)	0.061879843	0.023704550	0.00910085
Present method ($m = 20$)	0.061879843	0.023704550	0.00910084

Figure 2. The residual error of three equations in system of the model in $m = 20$.

6 CONCLUSION

In this study, a numerical method is presented for solving a model of HIV infection model of $CD4^+T$ cells. This method is based on Bernoulli polynomials and collocation method. The integration operational matrix of Bernoulli polynomials is derived. Next, by applying the operational matrix and collocation method, the model is solved, numerically. Finally, comparing the obtained results with some published results show the efficiency and accuracy of the present technique.

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